

April 30, 2024

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[DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.)

Factors Affecting Abdominal Fat in Chickens

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Received Date: 19-Jan-2024

Accepted Date: 23-Feb-2024

Published Date: 30-Apr-2024

Abstract

In broiler chickens, 15-20% of the total body weight consists of fat. The most variable carcass component in broilers is fat. Abdominal fat accounts for approximately 2-3% of live weight. In broiler chickens, age and gender have a significant effect on fat deposition. there is a correlation between body weight and the level of fat deposition. The differences in abdominal and carcass fat content between genotypes indicate the importance of genetic effects on fat storage. Nutrition factors have a significant impact on the carcass composition of broiler chickens. Generally, high-energy diets provide advantages for live weight gain and feed efficiency, but can lead to excessive fat deposition. Environmental factors such as ambient temperature, housing systems, lighting programs, and physical activities are directly related to the life span and physical activities of poultry and affect fat storage. The caliper tool was first developed to estimate abdominal fat thickness in live broiler chickens, and significant phenotypic correlations were found between with this technique and abdominal fat weight.

Keywords: Abdominal Fat in Chickens

Abdominal Fat In Chickens

As stated by Scheele et al., (1981); Griffin and Whitehead (1982) and Leenstra (1982), in broiler chickens, 15-20% of the total body weight consists of fat, and a minimum of 9 g/kg of fat is required for vital functions (Yoshida and Morimoto, 1970). 15% of the total fat is found in the blood and other tissues, while the remaining 85% is found in adipose tissue (abdominal fat, subcutaneous fat, intramuscular fat, etc.) (Evans, 1977). The most variable carcass component in broilers is fat (Lohman, 1973). Abdominal fat accounts for approximately 2-3% of live weight and is the most variable compared to other fat depots, according to Leenstra, 1986; Richard, 1975; Becker et al., 1979. Studies have reported that the coefficient of variation for abdominal fat (%25-30) is higher than that for total fat (%15-20) (Leenstra, 1984).

In broiler chickens, age and gender have a significant effect on fat deposition, with older birds and females having more fat than younger birds and males (%10-19 for females, %10-13 for males) (Edwards et al., 1973; Hakansson et al, 1978;) Lecrecq et al. 1980; Un, 1981; Grunder et al, 1987). Additionally, there is a correlation between body weight and the level of fat deposition, with rapid weight gain leading to an increase in fat tissue growth (Fisher, 1984). A 40% difference in abdominal fat level was observed among broiler chickens aged four to eight weeks (Griffiths et al., 1978). Growth in fat deposits occurs through an increase in the number of fat cells (hyperplasia) and an increase in the size of fat cells (hypertrophy). In laying and broiler-type chickens, fat growth is hyperplastic up to 14 weeks of age, and hypertrophic after 14 weeks (Pfaff and Austic, 1976; Marcii and Hansen, 1977; Hood, 1982; Hood, 1984). In broiler chickens, it

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has been reported that the increase in abdominal fat begins after four weeks of age and that fat growth is hyperplastic up to six weeks of age and hypertrophic thereafter (Cherry et al., 1984;). The increase in cell size is considered the main factor in determining abdominal fat (Simon and Leclercq, 1973).

Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) and Abdominal Fat

The feed conversion ratio (FCR) feed conversion ratio (FCR) is the amount of feed consumed per gram of live weight gain. A negative correlation has been reported between FCR and carcass fat Leenstra et al., 1987). On the other hand, Thomas et al. (Thomas et al., 1958; Thomas and Glazener et al. 1958) reported that the group with low FCR had higher abdominal fat compared to the group with high FCR. However, upon further investigation, Whitehead and Griffin (1984) reported that FCR was worse in the fatty (FL) line compared to the lean (LL) line when comparing chickens of the same live weight. Generally, due to the high correlation between low abdominal fat and high FCR, selection based on one of these traits results in improvement in the other as well (Cahaner et al., 1986).

The differences in abdominal and carcass fat content between genotypes indicate the importance of genetic effects on fat storage (Edwards and Denman, 1975). When compared to egg-laying chickens of similar age, broiler chickens have approximately twice as many fat cells, resulting in higher levels of abdominal fat (March and Hansen, 1977, March 1984). Significant differences in abdominal fat accumulation have been observed between fat and lean lines created based on various selection criteria (Whitehead and Griffin (1984).

Nutrition and Abdominal Fat

Nutrition factors have a significant impact on the carcass composition of broiler chickens (Un et al, 1980; McLeod, 1982). Generally, high-energy diets provide advantages for live weight gain and feed efficiency, but can lead to excessive fat deposition. In addition, the impact of energy/protein ratio imbalance on abdominal fat deposition is greater than its effect on carcass fat deposition (Jackson et al., 1982). Therefore, the energy level of feed should be kept at an optimum level to prevent deterioration of carcass quality (Freeman, 1983). Furthermore, the amino acid, fat, salt content (Lipstein, et al., 1975; Have et al., 1981; Marks and Washburn, 1983), and physical form of feed (grinding, pelleting, etc.) have a significant impact on fat storage (Pesti et.al, 1983; Marks and Pesti, 1984).

Although the fat transport system in the plasma of poultry is similar to that of mammals, the fat absorbed from the diet goes directly to the collecting vein without passing through the lymphatic system (Griffin, 1996). The liver is the main site of fat synthesis in poultry. Adipose tissue, where fat is stored, originates from very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL) synthesized in the liver or chylomicrons in the intestines that are rich in triglycerides (Gruffat et al., 1992-) Krogdahl, 1985).

The study by Barlov et al. (Bartov and Bornstein, 1976) reported that the relationship between carcass fat and plasma triglyceride levels was not suitable for predicting fat deposition in 8-week-old broiler chickens based on their experimental results. Similarly, in subsequent years, correlation between total plasma lipid concentration and abdominal fat accumulation could not be determined (Mirosh and Becker, 1983). In contrast, Griffin et al., 1982; Whitehead and Griffin, 1984 reported an important biochemical relationship (0.6-0.7) between body fat deposition and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) concentration in plasma in broiler chickens, and that this relationship could be used as a good predictor for determining body fat levels in live broiler chickens. By utilizing this biochemical relationship, selection studies were conducted based on high and low VLDL concentrations, and Lean Line (LL) and Fat Line (FL) lines were developed after 3 generations (Whitehead and Griffin, 1982; Whitehead and Griffin, 1986). Whitehead and Griffin, 1984 reported that plasma VLDL levels were 0.123 in males and 0.136 in females at the beginning of selection, and decreased after 3 generations (0.055 in males and 0.077 in females in the LL line), while they increased gradually in the FL line (0.164 in males and 0.177 in females). Similarly, from the third to the eighth generation, plasma VLDL and abdominal fat levels decreased continuously in LL lines, while they increased

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continuously in FL lines (Whitehead, 1990). Moreover, looking at the selection results of the seventh generation, it was reported that there was a significant difference between plasma VLDL (0.15 and 0.40) and abdominal fat (14.9 and 36.5 g/kg) levels in LL and FL lines, while the difference in live weights (2.24 and 2.18 kg) was not significant. In the eighth generation, they found a low correlation (0.12 in males and 0.15 in females) between plasma VLDL and abdominal fat levels in LL lines, while they found a high correlation (0.70 in males and 0.43 in females) in FL lines. After the eighth generation, significant differences were found in plasma VLDL concentration and body fat content between LL and FL lines (Griffin et al, 1991). In addition, they found a correlation of 0.88 between VLDL secretion rate and body fat content, and 0.74 between abdominal fat ratio and body fat content. The researchers reported that the source of the difference in fat synthesis between lines was the difference in proportional hepatic fat synthesis and proportional volatile fatty acid synthesis (Griffin et al, 1989). As a result, low proportional fatty acid synthesis and increased volatile fatty acid oxidation increased the utilization of proteins due to the differential effect of the LL line on hepatic amino acid oxidation, which led to an increase in protein utilization (Griffin et al, 1989).

Changes in the normal water and feed ratio can cause changes in abdominal fat levels in poultry (Marks,1994). Marks and Washburn, 1983 reported a decrease in abdominal fat content in broiler chickens with an increase in salt level in the diet, which led to an increase in water consumption. In another study, feeding a high protein diet resulted in an increase in normal water and feed consumption, which led to a decrease in abdominal fat levels (Marks and Pesti, 1984). In summary, studies support the idea that the inverse relationship between fat and water in the carcass, as suggested by Donaldson et al.(1956) and Twining et al. (1978), means that an increase in normal water intake leads to a decrease in abdominal fat. However, despite the use of different methods to show the relationship between water/feed ratio and abdominal fat, the reason for this difference has not yet been genetically determined (Darden and Marks, 1985-) Marks and Baik, 1994).

Based on the information provided by Mallard and Douaire (1988) and Ricard and Rouvier (1969), there is a relationship between abdominal fat and many body measurements in poultry, and they have shown that there is a negative relationship between breast and spine measurements and abdominal fat deposition. However, based on Chung et al. (1983), they have reported that this relationship is below the reliability level required to reduce abdominal fat levels in future generations commercially.

Limited feeding techniques can be used to reduce abdominal fat accumulation in chickens, either by reducing the amount of feed or by reducing the nutrient levels in the diet. In studies conducted, broilers fed with limited feeding showed lower abdominal fat accumulation than those fed ad libitum (Fisher and Wilson, 1974; Mollison et al., 1984; Zhong et al, 1995; Beyni and Habi, 1998). It has been observed that restricting energy intake at the beginning of the growth period leads to a decrease in fat storage (Pfaff and Austic, 1976; March and Hansen, 1977; Kubena et al., 1974). However, in a more recent study, it was reported that while the live weight of the free-fed group was 2.25 kg, the live weight of the group fed with 70% of the free-fed group was 1.67 kg, and the %AY (abdominal fat percentage) levels were 1.49 and 0.83, respectively (Beyni and Habi, 1998). As genetic potential increases, it becomes difficult to prevent fat deposition by using limited feeding techniques (Fontana et al., 1992). Both the difficulty in application and the decrease in live weight limit the economic feasibility of this technique.

Amino acid deficiency

Amino acid deficiency disrupts metabolism, causing changes in feeding patterns and reducing feed intake in proportion to the deficiency (Rogers and Leung, 1973; Boorman, 1979). The main reason for this is the rapid decrease in concentration of the limiting amino acid in the blood as a result of consumption of imbalanced feeds (Harper et al., 1970). On the other hand, it has been shown to affect animal behavior, causing a decrease in appetite and a second side effect of reduced growth and reproduction (87 Boorman, 1979). Picard et al. (1993), in a study to determine the reaction of chickens fed with a diet deficient in EAA (essential amino acids) to feed intake, found that the deficient feed was consumed 26% less in the first 24

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hours compared to the standard feed. The same researchers reported that when amino acid-sufficient and deficient feeds were offered to animals on a preferential basis, 65% of the consumed feed consisted of sufficient feed and 35% consisted of deficient feed within 7 hours.

In animals, low protein intake reduces nitrogen metabolism density and decreases the catabolism of amino acids, therefore the effect of amino acid deficiency is more pronounced in low protein diets (Harper et al., 1970). In their study, Pesti et al. (1994) showed that the genetic structure is effective in the relationship between plasma amino acid concentration and carcass composition, and reported that this is due to differences in genetic stocks in feed intake. In parallel, Boa-Amponsem et al. (1991) stated that genetic stocks may show different reactions to amino acid deficiency or imbalance. The differences in protein utilization between LL and FL lines may be due to genetic effects on protein synthesis and breakdown, as well as a result of increased amino acid oxidation in FL lines (Whitehead and Griffin, 1986).

Environmental Factors and Abdominal Fat

Environmental factors such as ambient temperature, housing systems, lighting programs, and physical activities are directly related to the life span and physical activities of poultry and affect fat storage. Kubena et al. (1972) and Fisher (1984) reported a positive correlation between total body fat and ambient temperature, with a linear increase of 0.19% in total body fat for every degree increase. Broiler chickens raised in cages have less activity and therefore deposit more fat than those raised on the ground (Deaton et al., 1974; Haye and Simons 1978). Lewis et al. (1994) reported that another environmental factor, lighting, did not have a significant effect on abdominal fat deposition, but intermittent lighting resulted in less fat accumulation.

The caliper tool was first developed to estimate abdominal fat thickness in live broiler chickens, and significant phenotypic correlations of 0.76 in males and 0.75 in females were found between the results obtained with this technique and abdominal fat weight (Pym and Thompson, 1980). In parallel, another research group used their own version of the caliper tool and found similar correlations (-0.77) between % abdominal fat and caliper measurements (Schwartzberg et al, 1980). It was suggested that this technique could be used as an indirect selection criterion for abdominal fat estimation in commercial broiler breeding programs and was implemented in breeding programs. However, in the following years, other researchers found variable and lower correlations when estimating abdominal fat using Pym's caliper method (Whitehead and Griffin, 1982; Chambers, 1982; Mirosh and Becker, 1983). The reasons for the low and variable results in studies using Pym's caliper technique, whether identical or modified, have been attributed to genetic variations, physical differences in the caliper tool, variations in the conducted studies, and individual differences among operators in using the tool (Marks, 1988).

Different Techniques and Abdominal Fat

Mallard and Douaire (1988) and Bentsen et al. (1986) used X-ray technology, which is commonly used in various fields of science, to determine different fat deposits in chickens. They reported significant correlations (0.70-0.90) between scanned fat areas. However, the high cost of this method limits its use in the industry. According to Mallard and Douaire (1988) and Robelin (1973) and Russeil (1987), there is a significant negative correlation (-0.7 and -0.86) between water and fat content in the carcass of farm animals. Mallard and Douaire (1988) reported that the method is not yet sufficient for indirect selection studies in their evaluation.

Another method for reducing abdominal fat accumulation is hormone application. Mitchell and Burke (1993) used TRH (thyrotropin-releasing hormone), Burke et al. (1987) used rcGH, and Huybrechts et al. (1992) used IGF-I (human insulin-like growth factor I) hormones on chickens, and they reported a reduction in abdominal fat by an average of 15%. However, the use of this method is not practical or economical.

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